

**To study mean extraction and mean exfoliation in Smokeless Tobacco Users and In The
Subjects with Periodontal Disease**

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ABSTRACT –Background - The mouth is filled with countless bacteria. Periodontal disease begins when certain bacteria in plaque (the sticky, colorless film that constantly forms on the teeth and the surfaces lining the mouth) produce toxins and enzymes that irritate the gums and

cause inflammation. The resulting inflammation, which may be painless, can damage the attachment of the gums and bone to the teeth. Resulting in extraction of teeth.

Objectives-This study was carried out to evaluate and compare the tooth loss in periodontal disease subjects and in subjects using smokeless tobacco to find out mean extraction and exfoliation .s

Materials and Method- : In the present study, 50 periodontal disease subjects and total 50 subjects taking smokeless tobacco were included as tobacco chewers 25; gutkha users 10 and mishri users 15 were included. Mean extraction and exfoliation was compared between periodontal disease patients (group I)and subjects taking chewing tobacco , gutkha and mishri .(group II- 1,2 & 3)We found mean extraction was less significant in group I patients than group II patients. Whereas mean exfoliation was found to be highly significant ($p < 0.0001$) in group II patients .Within tobacco chewers exfoliation was found significant in mishri users (group II-3)

Conclusion- These findings clearly shows that no. of tooth extraction was found more in periodontal disease than tobacco chewers and for tooth exfoliation was found significantly higher in tobacco users than in the patient with periodontal disease. Within tobacco groups ,group II- 3 patients shows maximum exfoliation.

Key words-Extraction, Exfoliation, Periodontal disease, Smokeless tobacco, Mishri, Gutkha.

Introduction-

On a simplistic level, our mouth is a barometer for our body. The condition of the gum tissue and other oral tissues can indicate hormone imbalances, vitamin deficiencies, and even undetected periodontal disease. The amount of saliva often reveals medication use. The content of your saliva may actually prove to be a biological monitor to find systemic disorders, possibly better than urine and blood, the fluids historically used.

There is also a correlation between substances put in the body and the systemic changes they create. For instance, tobacco users have a higher risk of periodontal disease, (1)

The word periodontal means "around the tooth." Healthy gum tissue fits like a cuff around each tooth. Where the gum line meets the tooth, it forms a slight v-shaped crevice called a sulcus. In healthy teeth, this space is usually three millimeters or less. Periodontal diseases are infections that affect the tissues and bone that support teeth. As the tissues are

damaged, the sulcus develops into a pocket that is greater than three millimeters. Generally, the more severe the disease, the greater the pocket depth and bone loss. The enlarged pockets allow harmful bacteria to grow and make it difficult to practice effective oral hygiene. Left untreated, periodontal diseases may eventually lead to tooth loss.(2)

Periodontal diseases, including gingivitis and periodontitis, are severe infections, and if left untreated, they can lead to tooth loss. Periodontal disease is a chronic bacterial infection that affects the gum tissue, bone, and attachment fibers that support the teeth and hold them in place in the jaw bone. It occurs when plaque (a soft, sticky, colorless film of bacteria) forms on the teeth and at the gumline and infects the gum tissue, causing gingivitis (inflammation and reddening of the gums). If periodontal disease is not treated with professional prophylaxis (teeth cleaning) and, in some cases, surgery, it can lead to moderate-to-advanced periodontitis and further destruction of the bone and gum tissue. Tooth loss may occur and teeth may have to be removed. (3,4)

Tobacco Chewing and host response-

Nicotine metabolites can concentrate in the periodontium and their effects include the promotion of vasoconstriction, and the impairment of the functional activity of polymorphs and macrophages. The numbers of neutrophils in peripheral blood are also increased by tobacco use and their migration through capillary walls is impaired also due to paralysis of the cell membrane. Tobacco Chewing has been demonstrated to activate the release of elastase, which has the capacity to cause tissue damage. (5)

In addition there is an increased production of oxygen species, which can lower tissue levels of alpha- 1 protease inhibitors so enabling elastase and other enzymes with potential for damaging tissue to remain unchecked at active sites. The gingival crevicular fluid levels of functional elastase and that complexed with the inhibitor have been demonstrated to be lower in Tobacco Chewers than controls. Much evidence on the effect of Tobacco Chewing on neutrophil activity suggests that these cells may accumulate at the site of inflamed periodontal tissues. As they may fail to migrate through the gingival crevice they can release their enzymes into the surrounding connective tissue therefore contributing directly to tissue

destruction. The reported lower levels of both salivary elastase and neutrophils in the oral cavity in smokers with periodontitis.(6,7)

Our study is concentrate on subjects taking chewing tobacco, gutkha , mishri and its effect on the extraction and exfoliation of teeth.

Aims and Objectives-

To study effects of tobacco use on oral health, with particular emphasis on the effects of periodontal diseases on tooth loss with assessment of gingival and periodontal status.

1. To study and compare extractions and exfoliations in periodontal disease and smokeless tobacco users.
2. To study and compare extractions and exfoliations in group- I, group II-1, group-II-2 and group –II-3 patients.(within groups).
3. To study all above parameters in either sex for male: female ratio.
4. To study all above parameters in different age groups.

Materials and Methods-

The present study was carried out in the Department of Periodontitis, In ,Vaidik Dental College and Research Center Daman . The patients selected for the present study were attending indoor/outdoor patient department from the Hospital. The clinical checkup of the patient was done by periodontist on the basis of detailed clinical history and clinical examination .The ethical committee of the Hospital and Dental College approved the research project work and all the patients gave written informed consent.

In the present study total 100 subjects were included. The distribution of these subjects was as follows.

Sr. no	Group	Types	No. of Subjects
1.	Group I	Periodontal disease subjects without tobacco users	50
2	Group II	Periodontal disease subjects with tobacco users	
		1- Gutkha Users	10
		2-Mishri Users	16
		3-Tobacco Chewers	24

Factors identified for periodontitis are age, gender, socioeconomic status, genetic Predisposition, , certain systemic conditions, illiteracy and Tobacco chewing. Tobacco chewing has been found to be a major environmental factor associated with generalized forms of severe periodontitis.

Study Design –

In the present study, 50 periodontal disease subjects and total 50 subjects taking smokeless tobacco were included as tobacco chewers 25; gutkha users 10 and mishri users 15 both male or female patients between the age group of 15-60 years were included.

The periodontal disease subjects were selected who were non smokers, non tobacco chewers.

Inclusion Criteria –

Study group (Group I): 50 subjects

- 1-Patients who did not use tobacco in smokeless or smoking form.
- 2-Patients with periodontal disease.

Study group (Group II): Total 50 subjects.

- 1-Patients using smokeless tobacco for more than 6 months
- 2-Patients with no history of any periodontal disease for the past 6 months.

Exclusion Criteria:

- 1- Patients with systemic diseases.
- 2- Pregnant or lactating females.
- 3-Tobacco users (e.g., Smokers)
- 4-Patients using any medication which affects the health of the periodontium.

Data collection-

Data were collected by two methods:

- 1-Using a questionnaire consisting of questions regarding daily oral hygiene and tobacco habits.
- 2-Clinical examinations were carried out under proper aseptic conditions using a mouth mirror, explorer, and William's Graduated Periodontal probe.

The following clinical parameters were recorded:

- 4- Average no. and mean of tooth extraction.
- 5- Average no. and mean of tooth exfoliation.
- 6- These parameters were recorded by a single examiner to prevent intra examiner differences

Study procedure:

After taking informed consents, all subjects were screened for inclusion and exclusion criteria. At base line all the clinical parameters were evaluated. The subjects were selected by the stratified random sampling method. The oral hygiene status of the subjects was evaluated using the simplified oral hygiene index.

Comparison for the clinical parameters among the four groups was carried out for the tooth loss in all groups. And the results were statistically compared.

Statistical Analysis –

Tooth extraction and exfoliation was carried between the periodontal subjects and (non tobacco) and Tobacco users i.e. gutkha , mishri and tobacco chewers was determined by using Pearson's chi-square analysis. P value of Probability values < 0.001 was considered as significant.

Results-Table 1: Age wise distribution of study subjects in Periodontal Disease and Tobacco user subjects i.e., Gutkha , Mishri and Tobacco Chewers.

Sr. No	Age Group	Non Tobacco		Tobacco Users		Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
1	16-20	3	6.0%	0	0.0%	3	3.0%
2	21-25	2	4.0%	4	8.0%	6	6.0%
3	26 -30	4	8.0%	2	4.0%	6	6.0%
4	31-35	9	18.0%	5	10.0%	14	14.0%
5	36-40	13	26.0%	11	22.0%	24	24.0%
6	41-45	4	8.0%	8	16.0%	12	12.0%
7	46-50	8	16.0%	5	10.0%	13	13.0%
8	51-55	3	6.0%	4	8.0%	7	7.0%
9	56-60	4	8.0%	10	20.0%	14	14.0%
10	61-65	0	.0%	1	2.0%	1	1.0%
Total		50	100%	50	100%	100	100%
Mean		39.20		44.40		41.80	
Standard Deviation		10.66		11.17		11.17	
Standard Error		1.51		1.58		1.12	

Sr. No	Age Group	Non Tobacco		Tobacco Users		Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
1	16-20	3	6.0%	0	0.0%	3	3.0%
2	21-25	2	4.0%	4	8.0%	6	6.0%
3	26 -30	4	8.0%	2	4.0%	6	6.0%
4	31-35	9	18.0%	5	10.0%	14	14.0%
5	36-40	13	26.0%	11	22.0%	24	24.0%
6	41-45	4	8.0%	8	16.0%	12	12.0%
7	46-50	8	16.0%	5	10.0%	13	13.0%
8	51-55	3	6.0%	4	8.0%	7	7.0%
9	56-60	4	8.0%	10	20.0%	14	14.0%
T Value		2.38					
P value		0.019					

(Study subjects in tobacco group are significantly older than those in non tobacco group)

Table No. 2 Different forms of tobacco use amongst the study subjects in tobacco chewers.

Sr. No	Type of Tobacco use	FEMALE		MALE		Total
		Number	percentage	Number	percentage	
1	Gutkha	1	10.0%	9	90.0%	10
2	Mishri	15	62.5%	9	37.5%	24
3	Tobacco chewing	5	31.2%	11	68.8%	16
Total		21	42.0%	29	58.0%	50

Table 3:

Sex wise

distribution of study subjects in Periodontal Disease and Tobacco user subjects i.e., Gutkha , Mishri and Tobacco Chewers.

Study Subject	Sex				Total
	Female	Percentage	Male	Percentage	
Non Tobacco	23	46.0%	27	54.0%	50
Tobacco	21	42.0%	29	58.0%	50
Total	44	44.0%	56	56.0%	100

CHI-

SQUARE=0.162, D.F.=1, P=0.687, Non Significant.

Table 4: Average number of extractions in Periodontal Disease (non tobacco) and Tobacco user subjects i.e., Gutkha , Mishri and Tobacco Chewers.

Study Subjects	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mann Whitney U Statistics	P value
Non Tobacco	0.50	0.95	1039	0.041
Tobacco	0.30	1.02		
Total	0.40	0.98		

(Number extractions in non tobacco users are significantly more than that in tobacco users.)

Table 5: Average number of exfoliations in Periodontal Disease and Tobacco user subjects i.e., Gutkha , Mishri and Tobacco Chewers.

Study Subjects	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mann Whitney U Statistics	P value
Non Tobacco	0.50	1.25	511	< 0.0001
Tobacco	2.75	2.42		

(Number of exfoliations in tobacco users are significantly more than that in non tobacco users)

Graph No.1 Average number of extractions and Average number of exfoliations in Periodontal Disease (non tobacco) and Tobacco user subjects i.e., Gutkha , Mishri and Tobacco Chewers.

From the graph it is clear that maximum exfoliations i.e. tooth loss was observed in the tobacco user patients.

Graph No. 2 Mean extractions and Mean exfoliations in different types of tobacco user subjects i.e. Gutkha , Mishri and Tobacco Chewers.

Discussion-

Table No.1- Shows age wise distribution of study subjects in periodontal disease and subjects taking tobacco, gutkha and mishri. It clearly indicates that as the age increases number of tooth loss increases and is found to be significant ($p < 0.01$) in the subjects taking tobacco as compare to the subjects with periodontal disease.

As the age increases the tobacco extracts affect monocytes, oral keratinocytes and production of inflammatory mediators, which may play a role in the development of these,

localized tissue alteration. The use of smokeless tobacco has been reported to cause tooth decay and discolouration of dental restorations. Chewing tobacco, in particular, is associated with an increased risk for dental caries because of higher sugar content, increased gingival recession, and enhanced collagenase activity. Abrasive particles in chewing tobacco may contribute to significant dental attrition, which may require dental restoration in advanced cases. It is suggested that smokeless tobacco users with co-existing gingivitis have high rates of gingival recession, mucosal pathology, and dental caries. Smokeless tobacco has also been associated with irreversible gingival attachment loss resulting in root exposure in aged subjects in tobacco chewers.

Table No.2-Indicates No. of subjects using chewing tobacco , gutkha and mishri .We found that out of 50 tobacco users Gutkha 10, Mishri 24 and tobacco chewers 16 .It clearly shows that maximum mishri users were found of these females were , Tobacco Chewers were 16, and only 10 gutkha users were found.

Table No.3- Shows Sex wise relationship in periodontal disease subjects and tobacco chewers'. It clearly indicates that there is no as such relation sheep in tooth loss and male and female ratio in periodontal disease group and tobacco users group.

Table No. 4- Shows average number of extractions in Periodontal Disease (non tobacco) and Tobacco user subjects i.e., Gutkha, Mishri and Tobacco Chewers.

Table No. 5- Indicates average number of exfoliations in Periodontal Disease and Tobacco user subjects i.e., Gutkha, Mishri and Tobacco Chewers.

Graph No.3 Exhibits average number of extractions and average number of exfoliations in Periodontal Disease (non tobacco) and Tobacco user subjects i.e., Gutkha , Mishri and Tobacco Chewers.

From table No., 4,5 and graph no.1&2 observes that no. of tooth extraction is little more in periodontal disease than tobacco chewers as well as exfoliation i.e. tooth loss is much higher in the tobacco users than in the patient with periodontal disease.

Moderate tobacco consumption can contribute to an increase in activated circulating monocytes and promote their adherence to endothelium. The role of cytokines has also been extensively examined in the pathogenesis of periodontitis. High levels of prostaglan- *PGE2*

have been associated with aggressive or early onset periodontitis and these elevated concentrations have been related to an increased responsiveness of circulating monocytes to bacterial challenge.

Influence of Tobacco Smoking on the Onset of Periodontitis in Young Persons (8) PGE_2 have been associated with aggressive or early onset periodontitis and these elevated concentrations have been related to an increased responsiveness of circulating monocytes to bacterial challenge .

The nicotine induced apoptotic modifications in Polymorphonuclear cells for up to (9) hours of culture time. These findings suggest nicotine exposure had a deleterious effect on the lifespan of neutrophils and modulation of their activities in respect to their crucial role in prevention of bacterial invasion of periodontal tissues. There appeared to be no effect on apoptosis of monocytes by nicotine exposure but these investigators did report that when stimulated by LPS monocytes exposed to nicotine had reduced IL-1_β release. This cytokine is proinflammatory and has been associated with osteoclast activity and alveolar bone resorption. Procoagulant activity expression is a function of monocytes related to limiting the spread of infections and its inhibition by nicotine is more evidence of the complexity of effect of tobacco

on this part of the host defense mechanism. Nicotine exposure can inhibit important antimicrobial activity such as production of superoxide anion and hydrogen peroxide. (6)

Tobacco consumption is clearly a high-risk behavior for the development of periodontal disease, and nicotine is the major vasoactive component in tobacco. Resulting in toothloss.

Tobacco is a major risk factor in the development and further progression of periodontal diseases. Cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) is an inducible enzyme believed to be responsible for prostaglandin synthesis at the site of inflammation. Currently, there is limited information on the regulation of COX-2 expression in smoking-associated periodontal disease. (10)

Decreased cell migration in periodontal wounds exposed to nicotine may be mediated through the Rac and PAK $\frac{1}{2}$ - p21 activated kinase pathway signaling pathways and results in periodontal disease.(11)

All of these findings suggest a possible role of micro organism in the tobacco users for exfoliation which results in major tooth loss.

CONCLUSION- With the above aims and objectives and the results obtained from our study it is evident from these investigations that tobacco in any form that is gutkha, mishri and raw tobacco leads to aggravation of already existing periodontal disease which has been revealed by statistical analysis and therefore it is necessary to educate and motivate population to refrain from the cause of tobacco in order to reduce incidence and prevalence of periodontal disease which has been found to be very high in our country.

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